

Gram-guided Error-correction for Highly-coherent Dictionaries and its Application to CS-ToF Imaging

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Abstract—During the design of any demodulation scheme in Compressive Sensing-based Time-of-Flight, we face two opposing criteria. On the one hand, we aim to minimize the number of measurements and, thus, the number of rows of the sensing matrix, to reduce acquisition times and approach real-time operation. On the other hand, we would like to recover the target’s depth in a grid as fine as possible to enhance the depth resolution. In this scenario, the sensing matrices become *fat* and their coherence close to the unit. In this paper, we present an original error-correction method to prevent from the appearance of depth estimation errors derived from this effect. Our algorithm first identifies the most correlated columns in the sensing matrix and then exploits the recovered depths over a pixel neighborhood to determine the most recommendable correction. Without loss of generality, we add this step to each iteration of Orthogonal Matching Pursuit and evaluate the performance gain.

Index Terms—Coherence, Compressive Sensing, Error-Correction, Orthogonal Matching Pursuit, Time-of-Flight

I. INTRODUCTION

Compressive Sensing (CS) techniques intend to develop sensing models capable of exactly reconstructing highly-sparse signals with high probability. This topic has a direct application to Pulse-based Time-of-Flight (PB-ToF) imaging systems based on coded modulation-demodulation schemes, as the reconstruction of a highly-sparse signal from a low-dimensional measurement vector, via a sensing matrix designed ad-hoc, is equivalent to the retrieval of the location(s) of the target(s) depth from few measurements in the time (depth) domain. Over the past few years, ToF imaging [1]–[3] has attracted much attention from the 3D imaging community because of the progressive reduction of the cost, size and power needs, together with an important enhancement of lateral and depth resolutions. In this respect, the generation of *good* sensing matrices plays a fundamental role, as more efficient sensing schemes lead to shorter acquisition times and alleviate the computational cost associated to the scene reconstruction.

The main contribution of this article is to propose a novel methodology which, making use of the correlations between the columns of the sensing matrix and exploiting an orthogonal domain such as the 2D pixel neighborhood, positively answers two relevant questions in CS as well as in coded-ToF imaging:

- 1) Can we practically predict the appearance of spurious depth estimates by making use of some inherent properties of the sensing matrix?
- 2) If so, can we employ this information to correct spurious values or, in other words, can we get a near-to-optimal scene reconstruction from a sub-optimal sensing matrix?

II. FUNDAMENTALS OF CODED TIME-OF-FLIGHT

In indirect PB-ToF cameras [4]–[6], a sequence of pulsed light signals in the Near Infrared (NIR) spectrum are emitted from a dedicated illumination source at a repetition frequency f_r , interact with the surrounding scene, and s return light paths are perceived by the pixel (or sensor). The response function of the scene \vec{x} can, then, be described as (1), being $\{\Gamma[k], \tau[k]\}_{k=0}^{s-1}$ the reflectivities and delays of s light paths captured by the pixel, and δ the Dirac function.

$$\vec{x} = \left[\sum_{k=0}^{s-1} \Gamma[k] \delta(t_j - \tau[k]) \right]_{j=1}^n \quad (1)$$

The depth and intensity of the target(s) are estimated from samples of the correlation of \vec{x} and m correlation functions generated in the imaging system. Each correlation function $[\vec{a}_i]_{i=1}^m$ can be expressed as the result of the convolution of an ideally (0,1)-binary pixel control signal $[\vec{a}_{0,i}]_{i=1}^m$ and the cross-correlation function $\vec{\eta}$, i. e., $\vec{a}_i = \vec{a}_{0,i} * \vec{\eta}$ [4], [7], which emulates the impulse response function of the ToF system and acts as a Gaussian filter of width $\sim \mathcal{O}(\text{ns})$.

$$y_i = \vec{a}_i \cdot \vec{x} = (\vec{a}_{0,i} * \vec{\eta}) \cdot \vec{x}, \text{ with } 1 \leq i \leq m \quad (2)$$

The retrieval of the target’s depth in a grid finer than the one given by the (0,1)-binary code $\vec{a}_{0,i}$ (depth super-resolution) requires dividing each of the n_0 elements of $\vec{a}_{0,i}$ in n_s sub-steps, prior to the convolution with $\vec{\eta}$. The system of equations described in (2) has no unique solution as $m \ll n$, being $n = n_0 \times n_s$ the total number of columns of the resulting sensing matrix \mathbf{A} . However, it leads to a linearly-constrained ℓ_0 -minimization problem when accounting for the sparsity (or compressibility) of \vec{x} in the time (or depth) domain (3), i. e., there exist only s targets to be recovered per observation direction corresponding to s non-zero entries in the sparse vector \vec{x} , with $s \ll n$ and $s \leq 2$ in most cases.

$$\hat{\vec{x}} = \arg \min_{\vec{x}} \|\vec{x}\|_0, \quad \text{subject to: } \vec{y} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \vec{x} \quad (3)$$

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This linearly-constrained ℓ_0 -norm minimization problem is non-convex and non-solvable in polynomial time. In order to ease and speed up the calculation, various schemes may be considered [8], [9]. Although our methodology can be implemented as an additional step in any sparsity-aware recovery algorithm, we propose to use Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) as a baseline, as it is generally faster than any classical constrained ℓ_1 -minimization solver [8], [10], and per-pixel processing would preclude real time if slower methods are used. In OMP a discrete probability function \vec{h} is built as the projection of the residual of the measurement vector \vec{y} onto the normalized columns of \mathbf{A} , and the depth of the target is given by the index of the maximum peak of \vec{h} . Moreover, the achievable depth super-resolution ($\delta_{\text{SR}} = n_s$), given by the fine discretization of \vec{a}_i in the depth or time domain, depends on the correct selection of operational parameters, such as emitted light pulse width and clock trigger frequency f_m , which have an impact on $\vec{\eta}$ and, thus, on the coherence (μ) of \mathbf{A} . These factors, dependant on each other, will be further discussed in Section III-B. In this respect, μ , given by the scalar product of the normalized columns of \mathbf{A} , is representative of the degree of similarity between $[\vec{a}^j]_{j=1}^n$. In case of $\mu = 1$, the inverse problem becomes ill-posed, as several identical columns exist over \mathbf{A} leading to ambiguities during the target's recovery.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Orthogonal Matching Pursuit and Gram-Guided Error-Correction

In OMP the exact target's reconstruction is ensured in the noiseless case if $\mu < \frac{1}{2s-1}$ [11], being s the sparsity of the signal being recovered. However, an erroneous determination of the support may occur for noisy signals and $s = 1$ when using highly-coherent dictionaries ($\mu \rightarrow 1$). In ϵ -OMP [12], Giryes and Elad coped with highly-coherent dictionaries by excluding from the feasible support highly-correlated columns with the ones already selected in the previous iteration by making use of the matrix of Gram \mathbf{G} , i.e., $g_j^k = \frac{\vec{a}^j \cdot \vec{a}^k}{\|\vec{a}^j\| \cdot \|\vec{a}^k\|} \leq \sqrt{1 - \epsilon^2}$. Although the methodology reliably explains how the energy distributes over the recovered signal domain, we find that it may lead to a reconstruction error in the presence of noise if the peak of \vec{h} is not correctly selected among the ones highly-correlated. In addition, ϵ -OMP yields OMP for $s = 1$. Differently, we make use of those highly-correlated columns to predict and possibly correct the determination of the target's location in each and from the first iteration of our algorithm ($s = 1$) by considering the recovered depths over the neighborhood of each pixel $\mathcal{N}(k, \omega) := \{i : \|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_k\|_\infty \leq \omega\}$, being \vec{r}_i and \vec{r}_k the 2D coordinates of the pixels i and k in the sensor array, respectively, and ω the neighborhood size. This methodology is suited for the detection and posterior correction of outliers, i.e., single depth estimation errors within large successfully recovered areas (see Fig. 3), which is the usual case in practice. The proposed methodology, coined Gram-guided Error-correction (GGEC), is described in Algorithm 1, and consists of four steps:

Algorithm 1: Gram-guided Error-correction method

Data: $[\vec{y}^k]_{k=1}^{M \times N}$, \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{G} , ϵ_0 , s , ω , α_d , κ
Result: $\vec{x}^{(k,s)}$

for $j = 1 : n$ **do**
 $\gamma_j := \{j\}$
 $\text{clos}(\gamma_j) = \left\{ \forall j \in \Gamma \mid k \neq j \text{ and } g_j^k \geq \epsilon_0 \right\}$
end
Initialize: $n_{\text{iter}} = 0$
for $k = 1 : M \times N$ **do**
 $\rho^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \emptyset$
 $\vec{x}^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \vec{0}$
 $\vec{r}^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \vec{y}^k$
 $\Phi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \emptyset$
end
while $n_{\text{iter}} < s$ and $\|\vec{r}^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}\|_2 < \epsilon$ **do**
 $n_{\text{iter}} = n_{\text{iter}} + 1$
 for $k = 1 : M \times N$ **do**
 $\vec{h} = \hat{\mathbf{A}}^\top \cdot \vec{r}^{(k, n_{\text{iter}} - 1)}$
 $j_{\text{max}}^k = \arg \max_{1 \leq t \leq \|\vec{h}\|_0} (h_t)$
 $\Phi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \left\{ \phi_t^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} \in \text{clos}(\{j_{\text{max}}^k\}) : |\phi_t^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} - j_{\text{max}}^k| > n_s \right\}$
 end
 for $k = 1 : M \times N$ **do**
 $\zeta_d = \max(\alpha_d \times \text{MAD}(j_{\text{max}}^{\mathcal{N}(\omega, k)}), \kappa \times n_s)$
 $\xi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \text{median}(j_{\text{max}}^{\mathcal{N}(\omega, k)})$
 if $|\xi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} - j_{\text{max}}^k| > \zeta_d$ **then**
 $l = \arg \min_{1 \leq t \leq |\Phi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}|} (|\phi_t^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} - \xi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}|)$
 $\rho^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \left\{ \rho^{(k, n_{\text{iter}} - 1)}, \phi_l^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} \right\}$
 else
 $\rho^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \left\{ \rho^{(k, n_{\text{iter}} - 1)}, j_{\text{max}}^k \right\}$
 end
 $\vec{x}^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \mathbf{A}^\dagger_{\rho^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}} \cdot \vec{y}^k$
 $\vec{r}^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} = \vec{y}^k - \mathbf{A}_{\rho^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}} \cdot \vec{x}^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}$
 end
end

- 1) Determination of the closure $\left\{ \text{clos}(\gamma_j) \right\}_{\epsilon_0, 1}$ (4) with $\gamma_j := \{j\}$, $1 \leq j \leq n$, and $\epsilon_0 := \sqrt{1 - \epsilon^2}$ from [12]. This set is given by the indices of the columns of \mathbf{A} whose cross-correlation with $\vec{a}^{j_{\text{max}}^k}$ is $\geq \epsilon_0$, with $\epsilon_0 \rightarrow 1$.

$$\Phi_j = \text{clos}_{\epsilon_0, 1}(\gamma_j) = \left\{ k \in \Gamma \mid k \neq j, g_j^k \geq \epsilon_0 \right\} \quad (4)$$

- 2) Initial estimation of the target's location perceived by each pixel $[j_{\text{max}}^k]_{k=1}^{M \times N}$ via OMP being M and N the number of rows and columns of the sensor array, and the corresponding set of feasible support candidates

Fig. 1. Sensing matrices generated upon random (0,1)-binary codes and corresponding Gram matrices and column cross-correlation factors with $f_r = 7$ MHz and $f_m = 448$ MHz and various illumination pulse widths.

$\Phi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})} \leftarrow \left\{ \text{clos}(\{j_{\text{max}}^k\}) \right\}_{\varepsilon_{0,1}}$ being the temporal sparsity n_{iter} such that $0 \leq n_{\text{iter}} \leq s$. We remove from $\Phi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}$ the candidates whose distance to j_{max}^k is $\leq n_s$, i. e., the number of sub-steps within each element of the (0,1)-binary code.

3) Determination of the threshold ζ_d given by the maximum between:

- a) $\alpha_d \times \text{MAD}(j_{\text{max}}^{\mathcal{N}(k, \omega)})$, α_d times the Median Absolute Deviation (MAD) [13] over the neighborhood $\mathcal{N}(k, \omega)$.
- b) $\kappa \times n_s$, which accounts for the depth variations at corners and edges, and the increase of highly-correlated columns in \mathbf{A} for longer pulses, being $\kappa \sim \mathcal{O}(1)$.

4) Conditional correction step, such that, if the distance between the initial guess j_{max}^k and the median value over the neighborhood $\xi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}$ exceeds the threshold ζ_d , the target's location is chosen as the element of $\Phi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}$ which minimizes the absolute distance to $\xi^{(k, n_{\text{iter}})}$.

B. Gain Limitations and Practical Aspects

Various demodulation schemes such as the gradient-Combinatorial approach proposed by Lopez Paredes *et al.* [14] and the ones designed by Gupta *et al.* [3] and Gutierrez-Barragan *et al.* [1] based on Hamiltonian codes on the hypercube graph, effectively prevent from the intersection of the coding curves or, in other words, reduce the likelihood of highly-correlated columns far from each other in \mathbf{A} . In this case, the columns identified in the set Φ_j are the result of the fine discretization of time (or depth) domain in the attempt of achieving super-resolution. In the aforementioned methodologies, the proposed error-correction step may not be effective as the detection of depth estimation errors is based on the presence of spurious outliers the depth of which significantly differs from the median depth over the pixel adjacency.

In addition, increasing the illumination pulse width leads to smoother correlation functions which, in practice, improve the recoverability for ideally 1-sparse vectors. This is illustrated in Fig. 1, which represents sensing matrices built upon $m = 10$ uniformly-distributed random (0,1)-binary codes characterized by a clock trigger frequency $f_m = 448$ MHz and for various pulse durations in terms of Full Width at Half Maximum FWHM ≤ 5 ns. However, a longer pulse yields a subsequent rise of power needs and, eventually, the deterioration of the sensing matrix properties (as the Root Mean Square (RMS)-value over \mathbf{G}) which may have an impact on the recovery performance in scenarios when transient profiles or reflective multi-path interference (MPI) ($s > 1$) are present.

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

A. Preliminary Considerations

We make use of the depth and intensity maps of two scenes in [15], which are characterized by different intensity levels, to validate the proposed approach. The maximum peak in the transient profile for each pixel is approximated to the nearest neighbor in the grid considered in our numerical simulations, and the depth estimation error is evaluated with respect to the position in the grid. In case of the intensity, the resulting scalar value for each pixel is multiplied by $\iota = 10^4$ to adjust it to the level of intensity expected during operation. Then, the maximum range (i. e., the repetition frequency) in the transient profiles is adjusted to 10 m to match the depths observed in the GT depth maps [15]. In order to allow for a fair comparison of the methodologies employing different m , we adjust the intensity of \vec{x} to ensure equal total exposure time budget. Then, the measurements are corrupted, accounting for the sensor readout noise, by adding normally distributed random noise, characterized by different standard deviations. Table I presents the typical design parameters of our prototype [5] working in semi-continuous rotation mode, being the observation direction fixed during acquisition.

Fig. 2. Depth estimation error obtained for the scenes bathroom (left) and bedroom (right) from [15] recovered via OMP (top) and OMP+GGEC (bottom) with $f_m = 448$ MHz and $f_r = 7$ MHz, for various noise levels, and FWHM = 0.5 ns, 1 ns, and 5 ns.

Fig. 3. **First row:** Recovered depth maps via OMP (left) and proposed OMP+GGEC (right) for one realization of a sensing matrix generated upon random (0,1)-binary codes with $m = 10$, $f_m = 448$ MHz, and $f_r = 7$ MHz, and additive random noise of std. dev. = 0.02. **Second row:** Column cross-correlations with respect to the recovered position for one pixel via OMP (failed) and OMP+GGEC (exact reconstruction).

B. Recovery Performance Gain with respect to Orthogonal Matching Pursuit

We evaluate two demodulation schemes traditionally employed in CS-ToF imaging, such as the ones built upon uniformly-distributed random (0,1)-binary codes, Scrambled Hadamard Ensembles (SHEs) plus (0,1)-rescaling, as well as two state-of-the-art sensing methodologies, such as gradient-Combinatorial [14] and the ones based on Gray and Hamiltonian codes [1], [3]. As described in Section III-B, the recovery

performance of a demodulation scheme significantly depends on the correct selection of the emitted light pulse width, which, in turn, is closely related to the clock trigger frequency f_m of the ToF sensor. In our numerical simulation, we consider $f_m = 448$ MHz, as this is the maximum achievable frequency for our camera prototype [5] during operation. Then, we evaluate three possible scenarios corresponding to very-short (FWHM = 0.5 ns), short-to-medium (FWHM = 1 ns) and long illumination pulses (FWHM = 5 ns).

Property	Symbol	Value
Clock trigger frequency	f_m	448 MHz
Repetition frequency	f_r	7 MHz
Number of sub-steps	n_s	6
Emitted light pulse width	FWHM	0.5 ns – 5 ns
Noise standard deviation	std. dev.	0.01 – 0.5
Camera non-ambiguous range	r_{max}	21.4 m
Outlier detection factor	α_d	6
Neighborhood size	ω	16
Closure threshold	ϵ_0	0.99
Resolution/scene correction factor	κ	3
Number of realizations	n_{real}	16

TABLE I

TYPICAL DESIGN PARAMETERS FOR OUR CAMERA [5] AND GGEC.

The results presented in Fig. 2 show a reduction of the depth estimation errors when considering random (0,1)-binary matrices and (0,1)-SHEs for moderate-to-high noise levels and short pulses, as the correction step prevents outliers caused by highly-correlated columns far apart from each other in \mathbf{A} . In case of gradient-Combinatorial and Gray-based approaches, we do not observe significant variations with respect to OMP because of the already close-to-optimal construction resulting in highly-correlated columns being very close to each other. For Hamiltonian-based ($m = 5$), the additional step yields a slight reduction of the depth error for short pulses. Moreover, no impact is observed for very-noisy signals, as the recovery generally fails over large areas of the array. In addition, GGEC does not yield significant changes in the estimation errors in both scenes for FWHM = 5 ns, as the absolute distance between the columns which belong to the identified closure is $< \zeta_d$. Finally, the most evident improvement in the recovery performance is observed for the sensing matrices built upon random (0,1)-binary codes and (0,1)-SHEs, with a reduction of the depth estimation error of up to one order of magnitude, which leads to results close to near-to-optimal construction methodologies for very-short and short-to-medium light pulses. In order to better illustrate the obtained performance gain, we present in Fig. 3 the depth maps recovered for both scenes via OMP (left) and OMP+GGEC (right) for one single realization of a random (0,1)-binary matrix and noise with std. dev. = 0.02. We find that the existence of highly-correlated columns far apart from each other in \mathbf{A} leads to large depth estimation errors when only OMP is considered, and that the error-correction step leads to a removal of the detected outliers and a drastic reduction of the depth estimation error. Additionally, in order to better illustrate how GGEC works, we present the column of \mathbf{G} corresponding to the incorrectly estimated target's position via OMP for one single pixel of each scene, in which the outlier is detected and the location is amended to yield a perfect match with the GT.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this paper, we have comprehensively described an original technique to correct the errors inherent in the demodulation scheme, by leveraging local correlations over the sensor array. We have evaluated its efficacy and demonstrated via

numerical simulations that it produces a net improvement on the recovery performance of demodulation schemes based on sensing matrices generated via random (0,1)-binary matrices and (0,1)-SHEs, yielding similar results as state-of-the-art methodologies [1], [3], [14] for noisy signals and short-to-medium pulses. Prospective work includes the evaluation of our methodology with real measurements and its extension to more complex scenes where reflective multi-path interference may be present, as well as the exploration of alternative solutions based on off-the-grid CS methods [16], [17].

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Gutierrez-Barragan, S. A. Reza, A. Velten, and M. Gupta, "Practical coding function design for Time-Of-Flight imaging," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR 2019, Long Beach, CA, USA, June 16-20, 2019*. Computer Vision Foundation / IEEE, 2019, pp. 1566–1574. [Online]. Available: http://openaccess.thecvf.com/content/CVPR/2019/html/Gutierrez-Barragan_Practical_Coding_Function_Design_for_Time-Of-Flight_Imaging_CVPR_2019_paper.html
- [2] A. Kadambi, R. Whyte, A. Bhandari, L. Streeter, C. Barsi, A. Dorrington, and R. Raskar, "Coded time of flight cameras: Sparse deconvolution to address multipath interference and recover time profiles," *ACM Transactions on Graphics (TOG)*, vol. 32, 11 2013.
- [3] M. Gupta, A. Velten, S. K. Nayar, and E. Breibach, "What are optimal coding functions for Time-of-Flight imaging?" *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 37, no. 2, Feb. 2018.
- [4] A. Bhandari, A. Kadambi, R. Whyte, C. Barsi, M. Feigin, A. Dorrington, and R. Raskar, "Resolving multipath interference in time-of-flight imaging via modulation frequency diversity and sparse regularization," *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 1705–1708, Mar 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://opg.optica.org/ol/abstract.cfm?URI=ol-39-6-1705>
- [5] A. Lopez Paredes and M. Heredia Conde, "On the formulation of coded demodulation and 3D reconstruction in rotating PB-ToF sensors," in *2023 31st European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO)*, 2023, pp. 1943–1947.
- [6] A. Lopez Paredes and M. Heredia Conde, "Practical low-density codes for PB-ToF sensing," in *ISCS 2023 - 2023 International Symposium on Computational Sensing*.
- [7] A. Bhandari, M. Heredia Conde, and O. Loffeld, "One-bit time-resolved imaging," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 42, no. 7, pp. 1630–1641, 2020.
- [8] P. Gill, A. Wang, and A. Molnar, "The in-crowd algorithm for fast Basis Pursuit denoising," *Signal Processing, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 59, pp. 4595 – 4605, 11 2011.
- [9] S. Chen and D. Donoho, "Basis pursuit," in *Proceedings of 1994 28th Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers*, vol. 1, 1994, pp. 41–44 vol.1.
- [10] H. Zou, "The adaptive LASSO and its oracle properties," *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, vol. 101, pp. 1418–1429, 02 2006.
- [11] J. A. Tropp, "Greed is good: Algorithmic results for sparse approximation," *Information Theory, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 50, pp. 2231 – 2242, 11 2004.
- [12] R. Giryes and M. Elad, "OMP with highly coherent dictionaries," 2013.
- [13] C. Leys, C. Ley, O. Klein, P. Bernard, and L. Licata, "Detecting outliers: Do not use standard deviation around the mean, use absolute deviation around the median," *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, vol. 49, pp. 764–766, 2013.
- [14] A. Lopez Paredes, M. Heredia Conde, and O. Loffeld, "Sparsity-aware 3D ToF sensing," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 1–1, 2023.
- [15] F. Gutierrez-Barragan, H. Chen, M. Gupta, A. Velten, and J. Gu, "iToF2dToF: a robust and flexible representation for data-driven Time-of-Flight imaging," *IEEE Transactions on Computational Imaging*, vol. 7, pp. 1205–1214, 2021.
- [16] G. Tang, B. N. Bhaskar, P. Shah, and B. Recht, "Compressed sensing off the grid," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 59, no. 11, pp. 7465–7490, 2013.
- [17] L. F. O. Chamon, Y. C. Eldar, and A. Ribeiro, "Functional nonlinear sparse models," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 68, pp. 2449–2463, 2020.